

RESPONSE OF BIO-SLURRY BASED COMPOST ON SOIL PROPERTIES AND YIELD OF MATURE TEA

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Abstract

A field experiment was conducted at the Bangladesh Tea Research Institute (BTRI) farm from January 2022 to December 2022 to evaluate the effect of bio-slurry based compost applications on the yield of mature tea (*Camellia sinensis* L.). At the same time, the use of inorganic fertilizers was minimized with the gradual increase of doses of bio-slurry based compost. Compost and chemical fertilizers were administered in varying amounts in six distinct treatments, each with three replications. The plucking data was recorded every seven days during the harvest season. The highest yield (1968 kg/ha) of made tea was recorded in the treatment T₆, where 6 t/ha bio-slurry based compost with 40% of the recommended dose of chemical fertilizer was applied. The rate of increase over control was 19.64%. In contrast, the treatment T₄ (3 tons/ha bio-slurry based compost + 70% of the recommended dose of chemical fertilizer) was found more effective considering the economic viewpoint. The maximum usage of bio-slurry based compost and the reduced rate of chemical fertilisers from the recommended dosages enhanced tea production, and the increase in yield due to varied treatments was statistically significant ($F = 3.51, p < 0.05$). Besides the highest yield, the treatment T₆ plot showed a maximum increase in organic carbon (1.24 ± 0.07 %), total nitrogen (0.128 ± 0.01 %), available phosphorus (104.76 ± 3.72 mg/kg) and calcium (303.03 ± 4.08 mg/kg).

Keywords: Bio-slurry, compost, chemical fertilizer, yield, tea

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Introduction

As a perennial crop, growing tea requires a prolonged period of monoculture cultivation (Phukan et al., 2019). Managing nutrient levels in the tea field is crucial, and chemical fertilizers are the primary source of nutrient supply for tea plants. The dependency on chemical fertilizers has decreased the amount of organic matter and beneficial microbes in the tea garden soils, reducing the soil's tilth and fertility (Zohora et al., 2022). In addition to harming the environment, heavy and frequent applications of mineral fertilizers deteriorate soil properties. Alternative approaches are being sought after due to the excessive expense of chemical fertilizers, the widening gap between supply and demand, and their detrimental effects on the environment. However, it is generally acknowledged that the secret to increasing crop productivity is to apply fertilizer in a balanced manner while effectively using other inputs (Gebrewold and Yildiz, 2018).

An alternative strategy for effectively and economically regulating soil fertility to achieve sustainable crop production is the integrated nutrient management system (Han et al., 2016). As an alternative, the integrated nutrient management system uses less inorganic fertilizer and combines it with organic resources, including composts, crop residues, animal manures, and green manure (Chen, 2008). Using organic and inorganic fertilisers in tandem plays a vital role in maintaining soil fertility. In particular, the combination of organic and inorganic

fertilizers leads to a more significant increase in microbial biomass and improves soil health (Elkholy et al., 2010). It lowers the cost of suggested inorganic fertilizer and increases its effectiveness of usage (Abedi et al., 2010). The optimal combination of mineral and organic fertilizers depends on the ecological circumstances and land use system.

The use of different types of compost as a source of organic fertilizers is being very popular nowadays. Bio-slurry is an organic substance produced as a byproduct of biogas facilities via anaerobic digestion of methane gas. It can be used in liquid, compost, and dry form and is a very good fertilizer/composting substance for crops (Warnars and Oppenoorth, 2014). On the other hand, bio-slurry from biogas digesters has an average plant nutrient content of about 0.75% nitrogen, 0.65% phosphorus and 1.05% potassium (Demont et al., 1991). According to Abubaker et al. (2015), bio-slurry prevents ammonia oxidation and denitrification, improving plant performance by reducing soil nitrogen losses. However, very few experimental investigations have explored the effects of bio-slurry based compost applications on the yield of tea and changes in tea garden soil properties. This study sought to ascertain the optimal dosage of bio-slurry-based compost and how it affected tea productivity, which can be used to ensure cost-effective use of chemical fertilizers in sustainable tea production.

Materials and Methods

An experiment was carried out at BTRI Farm (24° 17' 36.8" N and 91° 44' 49.5" E) to evaluate the impact of bio-slurry based compost on the characteristics of the soil and the production of mature tea. The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Block Design, having 6 treatments with three replications. The unit plot size was 4.2 m × 2.5 m. Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K) nutrients were applied through urea, triple super phosphate (TSP) and muriate of potash (MOP), respectively, based on the average yield of the experimental site. Before fertilization, dolomite was applied in every experimental plot except for the control, which depended on soil pH and sufficient soil moisture. Chemical fertilizers were applied after a good shower of rain of 15-20 cm. Urea and MOP fertilizer were applied in two splits and TSP fertilizer was applied during the 1st split application in the cropping season. The first dose of fertilizer was applied in April, and the second dose in the first week of August 2022. Bio-slurry-based compost was applied and mixed with the soil by light forking in two splits 15 days before chemical fertilizer application. During the tea-harvesting season, the weight of the green leaves was recorded every seven days to determine the yield. Intercultural activities, including pruning, irrigation, and pest control were carried out as and when required.

Treatment details

T₁ = Control (No organic manure and chemical fertilizer)

T₂ = 100% RCFD* (N¹⁰⁰, P³⁰, K⁶⁰ kg/ha)

T₃ = 1.5 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 85% RCFD

T₄ = 3.0 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 70% RCFD

T₅ = 4.5 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 55% RCFD

T₆ = 6.0 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 40% RCFD

*RCFD= Recommended Chemical Fertilizer Dose

Soil sample collection and analysis method

In order to measure various soil physio-chemical parameters, such as soil texture, pH, organic carbon (%), total nitrogen (%), available phosphorus (mg/kg), potassium (mg/kg), calcium (mg/kg), and magnesium (mg/kg), initial and post-harvest soil samples were taken from a depth of 0-23 cm by using the soil sampling tools called 'Auger'. Soil texture was determined by the hydrometer method. A pH metre (WTW InoLab pH 7110) was used to determine the pH of the soil samples. The soil suspension was made using distilled water at a ratio of 1:2.5 soil to water (Huq and Alam, 2005). Walkley and Black's wet oxidation method (1934) was used to quantify the amount of organic carbon in the soil. For the determination of total nitrogen Micro Kjeldahl steam distillation method was applied (Huq and Alam, 2005). Colorimetric estimation of available phosphorus was done using the ascorbic acid method (Murphy and Riley, 1962). Available potassium, calcium and magnesium were extracted with 77% ammonium acetate solution (Peterson, 2002). Available K was determined by flame photometer (BUCK-Scientific PEP7), while calcium and magnesium were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Analytik Jena novAA 400P).

Compost analysis method

Physical and chemical analysis of the applied bio-slurry based compost was done before field application. The moisture % was calculated as a percentage for the compost using a moisture analyzer (KERN DBS60-3). The organic carbon (%) of the compost was determined by using Muffle Furnace (JISICO. Model: J-FM-28) at 550°C as reported by Yeomans and Bremner (1988). The pH of the compost was determined in compost-water suspension (1:10) according to Jodice et al. (1982) by using a pH meter (WTW InoLab pH 7110). Total nitrogen (N) was ascertained by utilizing the Micro Kjeldahl steam distillation technique (Huq and Alam, 2005). Total P was determined by the colorimetric method (Blue color method) using a spectrophotometer (JENWAY 6300) (Peterson, 2002). For determination total potassium (K), total calcium (Ca), total magnesium (Mg), total zinc (Zn) and total Copper (Cu) of the compost sample were digested by the nitric acid-perchloric acid digestion method and determined using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (Analytik Jena novAA 400P) as described by Huq and Alam, 2005.

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses, such as descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and DMRT (Duncan's multiple range test) were performed using the statistical software SPSS version 20.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Partial budget analysis, such as gross return and net return for every treatment applied to the yield of tea was calculated.

Results and Discussion

Physico-chemical analysis of bio-slurry based compost applied in the experimental plots reveals that, most of the nutrient content and other properties were within the critical limits set by the Bangladesh government (Table 1).

Tea may be produced on a variety of geologically derived soils. In Bangladesh quaternary and recent alluvial soils are prevalent. Low fertility, high acidity, and heavy weathering characterise tea garden soils. In addition, flooding does not deposit fertile silt on these soils; rather, it suffers from erosion (Saha et al., 2022). The soil analytical results showed that the study area had a pH, organic carbon (O.C), total nitrogen (N), available phosphorus (Av. P), available calcium (Av. Ca), and available magnesium (Av. Mg) within the critical limit and available potassium (Av. K) below the critical limit of tea soil (Table 2).

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of bio-slurry based compost.

Parameter	Analytical result	Government Approved Critical Limits (Ahmed et al., 2018)
Color	Dark Gray	Dark Grey to Black
Odor	Absence of foul odor	Absence of foul odor
Physical Condition	Non granular	Non granular
Moisture%	18.46	10 - 20
pH	7.2	6.0 - 8.5
Organic Carbon %	10.13	10 - 25
Total Nitrogen %	1.72	0.5 - 4.0
C:N	8:1	20:1(max)
Total Phosphorous %	2.65	0.5 - 3.0
Total Potassium %	0.53	0.5 - 3.0
Total Calcium %	2.11	-
Total Magnesium %	0.24	-
Total Zinc %	0.03	0.1 (max)

The pH values of the treatment plot were significantly ($p < 0.05$) affected by the treatments compared to control (Table 3). It was observed that the pH values of soil decreased in the treated areas over control, and the lowest value was found in T₄ and T₆ where 3 tons/ha and 6 tons/ha bio-slurry based compost were applied with 70% and 40% of the recommended dose of chemical fertilizer. The decrease in pH in almost every treatment might be due to the release of organic acids from the compost (Ding et al., 2020).

Table 2. Initial soil fertility in the experimental field.

Location	Texture	pH	O.C (%)	Total N (%)	Av. P (mg/kg)	Av. K (mg/kg)	Av. Ca (mg/kg)	Av. Mg (mg/kg)
BTRI Farm	SCI	5.8	1.06	0.12	71.74	43.89	202.09	39.92
Critical value	SL - L	4.5-5.5	1.0	0.1	10	80	90	25

The soil's organic carbon content increased relative to its initial value throughout each treatment except for treatment T₁ and T₂. The addition of chemical fertilizer did not cause the soil's organic carbon content to rise above its initial point; nevertheless, the treatments showed a more significant accumulation of organic carbon where bio-slurry based compost was applied. The plots treated with treatment T₆ had the highest increase in organic carbon ($1.24 \pm 0.07\%$) followed by T₅ and T₃ treated plots. The direct absorption of organic matter through organic manure in the soil may be the cause of the enhanced organic carbon content of the soil in the plots receiving the combined application of inorganic fertilisers and bio-slurry based compost (Saha et al., 2022). In addition, the close proximity of all the plots to one another may have had an impact on the organic carbon content of the plots.

Table 3. The results of soil analysis at the completion of the experiment.

Treat ment	Texture	pH	O.C (%)	Total N (%)	Av. P (mg/kg)	Av. K (mg/kg)	Av. Ca (mg/kg)	Av. Mg (mg/kg)
T ₁	SCI	5.8 ± 0.06 a	1.06 ± 0.04 c	0.127 ± 0.02 b	72.97 ± 6.69 c	40.07 ± 4.21 b	207.90 ± 4.24 c	40.87 ± 1.41 d
T ₂	SCI	5.7 ± 0.07 ab	1.03 ± 0.03 c	0.108 ± 0.01 a	83.94 ± 4.32 bc	53.06 ± 8.50 ab	211.73 ± 7.37 c	45.79 ± 1.57 d
T ₃	SCI	5.5 ± 0.13 abc	1.15 ± 0.04 abc	0.119 ± 0.01 a	87.16 ± 6.88 b	42.07 ± 7.22 b	288.30 ± 8.29 ab	94.21 ± 2.11 a
T ₄	SCI	5.3 ± 0.12 c	1.09 ± 0.04 bc	0.111 ± 0.01 a	87.33 ± 6.70 b	43.90 ± 5.47 b	275.57 ± 3.55 b	71.75 ± 1.82 b
T ₅	SCI	5.5 ± 0.09 bc	1.22 ± 0.04 ab	0.119 ± 0.03 a	94.25 ± 3.69 ab	69.35 ± 5.98 a	295.47 ± 8.36 ab	60.76 ± 3.07 c
T ₆	SCI	5.3 ± 0.06 c	1.24 ± 0.07 a	0.128 ± 0.01 a	104.76 ± 3.72 a	65.01 ± 5.15 a	303.03 ± 4.08 a	75.06 ± 2.87 b

Note: Mean \pm standard error within each row followed by a different letter indicates significant differences at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT).

The plot treated with 6.0 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost with 40% recommended chemical fertilizer showed a maximum increase in total nitrogen ($0.128 \pm 0.01\%$). The build-up of organic matter brought on by applying organic manure may be the reason for the rise in the total N content in the soil under the treatments. Additionally, organic matter decreased nitrogen losses, increasing the amount of total nitrogen in the system. Several studies revealed that the total N and organic C content of the soil, as well as the amount of accessible nutrients, are all significantly increased when inorganic and organic fertilizers are used together, improving the overall characteristics of the soil (Ali et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2014 Mahmood et al., 2017; Redda and Kebede, 2017).

The available phosphorus content of the soil over its initial concentration was increased in every treatment, including control. The addition of phosphatic fertilizers might cause an increasing trend of phosphorus concentration in experimental plots. Plots treated with 6 tons/ha bio-slurry based compost with 40% of the recommended dose of chemical fertilizer showed the highest increase in available phosphorus (104.76 ± 3.72 mg/kg) relative to its initial value. Research has demonstrated that additions of organic manure can influence the adsorption and desorption of P in soil and directly raise the P pool in soils (Johan et al., 2021).

The content of available potassium (mg/kg) in soil was found to significantly ($p < 0.05$) vary among the treatments, and the maximum potassium (69.35 ± 5.98 mg/kg) content was found in treatment T₅ treated plots where 4.5 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost and 55% of recommended doses of chemical fertilizers were applied together. The results also revealed that there were no significant differences between the treatments T₅ and T₆.

On top of that, the concentrations of available calcium (Ca) and available magnesium (Mg) were also significantly ($p < 0.05$) varied among the treatments over the control. The concentrations of calcium in every plot were increased over the control. The concentrations of Ca in different treatments decreased in order: T₆ > T₅ > T₃ > T₄ > T₂ > T₁. Meanwhile, the highest concentration of Mg was recorded in the plots receiving treatment T₃. The annual dolomite application may cause the soil's rising Ca and Mg contents (Saha et al., 2022).

Fig. 1. Bar chart showing the effect of different treatments on the yield of tea. Figures in the parentheses above each bar represent the rate of increase over control. The different letters within each bar indicates significant differences at $p < 0.05$ according to Duncan's multiple range test (DMRT).

The impact of different treatments on the mean yield of tea is illustrated in Fig. 1. The outcome shows that the mean yield over control rose with each treatment. Yields obtained from different treatments reveal that a comparatively higher mean yield of 1968 kg/ha was

obtained from the treatment T₆ (4.5 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 55% RCFD) that was closely followed by the yield of 1943 kg/ha from the treatment T₅ (3.0 tons/ha Bio-slurry based compost + 70% RCFD). The lowest yield of 1645 kg/ha was obtained from the treatment T₁ where no fertilization was done. However, from the result, it was observed that the highest yield increase was found in treatment T₆ (19.64 %) followed by treatment T₅ (18.12%) over control and the lowest yield increase over control was found in treatment T₂ (4.07%). The yield increase from various treatments was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

In the present study, it has been observed that there was no significant difference between T₅ and T₆, which means applying bio-slurry based compost @ 4.5t/ha with 55% recommended fertilizer dose was as effective as bio-slurry based compost @ 6t/ha with 40% recommended chemical fertilizer dose. However, there were significant differences between the treatments mentioned in T₁ and T₂. There was also significant variation between treatment T₄ and T₁. Saha et al. (2022) reported that a higher tea yield was obtained by combining organic and inorganic fertilizers. It was reported that applying bio-slurry increased 11% yield of tea, whereas, in the present study, the yield increased to 19.64% (SNV, 2011). Several earlier studies support the following conclusions: The application of bio-slurry increases the growth and yield characteristics of field crops and delivers both macronutrients (N, P, K) and micronutrients (Zn, Mn, B) (Islam et al., 2010; Kumar et al., 2015; Ferdous et al., 2020; Roeswitawati et al., 2021).

Table 4. Partial budget analysis of the treatments applied to the yield of tea.

Treatment	Yield of	Variable Cost			Gross Return	Net Return
	Made Tea	Fertilizer	Labour	Total		
	(kg/ha)		(Tk/ha)			(Tk/ha)
T ₁	1645	0	0	0	296100	296100
T ₂	1712	10304	850	11154	308160	297006
T ₃	1768	20756	3400	24156	318240	294084
T ₄	1903	31195	5780	36975	342540	305565
T ₅	1943	41647	8160	49807	349740	299933
T ₆	1968	52141	10540	62681	354240	291559

Note: Gross return = yield \times price of a particular product; net return = gross return - variable cost. Assuming, the price of bio-slurry based compost = 8 Tk/kg, Urea = 22 Tk/kg, TSP = 20 Tk/kg and MOP = 13 Tk/kg, made tea = 180 Tk/kg, labour wage = 170 Tk/day.

The partial budget analysis of the treatments applied on the yield of tea (Table 5) indicated that the highest net return was found in the treatment T₄ (305565 Tk/ha), which was followed by the treatment T₅ (299933 Tk/ha), T₂ (297006 Tk/ha), T₁ (296100 Tk/ha) and the lowest net return was found in the treatment T₆ (291559 Tk/ha). Therefore, compared to the treatment T₁, almost all applied treatments were economically viable except T₃ and T₆. Although the highest yield of tea was found in the treatment T₆, the highest net return was obtained from treatment T₄. Hence, the dose 3 tons/ha bio-slurry based compost with 70% RCFD is more effective considering the economic viewpoint.

Conclusion

The management of tea plantations heavily depends on the supply of nutrients, which is mostly achieved by chemical fertilisers. However, it is widely accepted that a balanced fertiliser application along with efficient use of other inputs is the key to raising crop output. By using 3 tons/ha bio-slurry based compost in tea plantation can reduce 30% use of chemical fertilizers and thus ensure agricultural sustainability and further reduce environmental pollution. The findings revealed that applying bio-slurry based compost and chemical fertilizers combinedly has some significant advantages in the production of tea and improvement of tea soil quality.

Acknowledgements

The authorities of Bangladesh Tea Board and the Director of Bangladesh Tea Research Institute are acknowledged by the authors for providing the required resources.

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